

H2020 - Research and Innovation Action

APPLICATE

Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE

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Data catalogue and services

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A framework for connecting physically distributed data centres into a unified unit has been implemented and put in operation for APPLICATE. This provides mechanisms for documenting data, searching for data, accessing data, transforming data and visualising data. The human front end to the system is available at <https://applicatemet.no/>.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and objectives

Vines et al. (2013) showed that “The availability of research data declines rapidly with Article Age. A consequence of the decline can be that 80% of the data are not available after a period of 20 years after the publication of the article.

The purpose of this task was to provide a framework for structured data management including sharing and consumption within the project and to ensure long term data preservation as required for the data produced. APPLICATE is following a distributed data management approach similar to Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) and Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) where data are managed by a set of physically distributed data centres that are connected.

1.2 Organisation of this report

This report provides a brief introduction to the APPLICATE data management. First a brief description of the approach is provided, followed by a system description and presentation of the graphical interface.

METHODOLOGY

This approach used in APPLICATE is a continuation of the efforts undertaken during the International Polar Year where data were hosted and managed in a collection of physically distributed data centres. However, in the context of APPLICATE not much was known of the data centres that would contribute to the project, except that the data centres hosted by

- Norwegian Meteorological Institute
- Alfred Wegener Institute
- European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts

would contribute. The Norwegian Meteorological Institute would set up the central node based on the experience gained during the International Polar Year, WMO Global Cryosphere Watch and a number of other operational and scientific projects.

In order to connect the distribute data centres into a unified system, discovery metadata are used. Discovery metadata are like library index cards describing books, but in this context datasets and how to access the datasets.

The central node in the APPLICATE data management system, that is the APPLICATE Data Portal, harvests discovery metadata from the contributing data centres and ingests these in a searchable catalogue. The harvest of discovery metadata can be automated using interoperability protocols or manually when the data provider sends a discovery metadata record by email or similar to the portal which ingests this.

The system for harvesting discovery metadata, ingesting and handling the information in these discovery metadata records have been developed over several years. However, the specific version used by APPLICATE is quite new and some issues were detected when launching this in support of APPLICATE.

Figure 1: Schematic overview of the system setup for the APPLICATE Data Management.

A schematic overview of the system is provided in Figure 1. In order to connect the physically distributed data centres, a number of services are required. These services harvests discovery metadata, makes discovery metadata searchable, utilises the machine services identified by the discovery metadata in web clients etc. A critical issue in the approach selected is the need for standardised documentation of data, both at the discovery level and the use level. This is further described in Deliverable D6.3.

Figure 2: Schematic outline of the hardware framework used for the APPLICATE central portal connecting the physically distributed data centres.

In order to support the setup outlined in Figure 1 a hardware setup is required. This is outlined in Figure 2. It only describes the environment for the APPLICATE Data Portal, not the data centres contributing to the APPLICATE Data Management system. In the context of APPLICATE, the latter are only accessed through the web services offered for accessing the discovery metadata and the actual data. Most of the web services used within the APPLICATE Data Portal are operated in a private cloud running OpenStack. Some of the services are operated in a High-Performance Computing environment running through OpenGridEngine, but none of these are available to people nor machines external to the environment where the APPLICATE data management is running. In fact only two services are available externally, all other services are consumed within the external services offered. All web services are running through secure communication to ensure the integrity of information from disk to user. However, not all external data centres are running secure communication at present. The user will be warned by the web browser when this is happening.

In Figure 2 WMO Global telecommunication System (GTS) is indicated. Work is ongoing to extract information from WMO GTS and make this available for the APPLICATE community.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The APPLICATE Data Portal and accompanying services are available through <https://applicatemet.no/>.

The current front view is presented in Figure 3. The menu system is shown on the top of the page. The menu choice marked “Support” provides some background information for the data providers (further presented in Deliverable D6.3) as well as issue trackers for both the data management system and the APPLICATE Post processing environment. The menu marked “Available datasets” provides the human search interface used to find relevant datasets. It can readily be seen that it is possible to search by free (full) text, data collection period, spatial bounding box, institutions, principal investigators and scientific keywords describing the variables. For the latter NASAs Global Change Master Directory Science Keywords are used.

The results of a search is shown in Figure 5. This tabular and provides information extracted from the discovery metadata along with interfaces to the data. The service level for a dataset depends on the interoperability interfaces offered for the dataset by the data centre hosting the data.

Figure 6 shows a dataset where the host data centre provides higher order interoperability interfaces to the data. In addition to downloading the data, this also provides a transformation interface relying on the Open Data Protocol (OPeNDAP) as well as visualisation using OGC Web Mapping Service. The first allows the user to subset the data (i.e. extract only parts of the dataset), the latter visualisation (see Figure 7). The visualisation can handle timeseries, as indicated by the time slider in Figure 7, support for vertical layers is under development.

Figure 1: APPLICATE Data Portal front page.

Figure 2: The search results tabulation.

Figure 3: Dataset with higher order services supported by the host data centre.

Figure 4: Illustration of the Web Map Service client.

CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The APPLICATE Data Portal and backend services are up and running. It will require some further development during the project period but can be used as an efficient tool to find and assess data. Work is ongoing to remove some issues identified. This will make it more reliable and robust, but also new functionality is under development. In particular support for time series at weather stations and radiosoundings are currently under development. This will add some more backend services to the system.

The next steps include a number of system updates to correct the issues detected so far. These will be done within the first quarter of 2018. Subsequent updates with new functionality is planned mid 2018 and early 2019.

REFERENCES

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